

Multilayer perceptron

Neural networks are used in many predictive data mining applications because of their power, flexibility, and ease of use when the underlying process is complex [1-10].

Neural networks used in predictive applications, such as the multilayer perceptron (MLP) network, are supervised in the sense that the model-predicted results can be compared against known values of the target variables [1-10].

The MLP has a feedforward architecture because the connections in the network flow forward from the input layer to the output layer without any feedback loops. The input layer contains the predictors. The hidden layer contains unobservable nodes; or units. The value of each hidden unit is a function of the predictors; the exact form of the function depends in part upon the network type and in part upon user-controllable specifications. The output layer contains the responses (predicted variables). Each output unit is a function of the hidden units. The exact form of the function depends, in part, on the network type, and in part on user-controllable specifications [1-10].

Notation:

The following notation is used for multilayer perceptrons unless otherwise stated:

$X^{(m)} = (x_1^{(m)}, \dots, x_P^{(m)})$	Input vector, pattern m , $m=1, \dots, M$.
$Y^{(m)} = (y_1^{(m)}, \dots, y_R^{(m)})$	Target vector, pattern m .
I	Number of layers, discounting the input layer.
J_i	Number of units in layer i . $J_0 = P$, $J_I = R$, discounting the bias unit.
Γ^c	Set of categorical outputs.
Γ	Set of continuous outputs.
Γ_h	Set of subvectors of $Y^{(m)}$ containing 1-of- c coded h th categorical field.
$a_{i:j}^m$	Unit j of layer i , pattern m , $j = 0, \dots, J_i$; $i = 0, \dots, I$.
$w_{i:j,k}$	Weight leading from layer $i-1$, unit j to layer i , unit k . No weights connect $a_{i-1:j}^m$ and the bias $a_{i:0}^m$; that is, there is no $w_{i:j,0}$ for any j .
$c_{i:k}^m$	$\sum_{j=0}^{J_{i-1}} w_{i:j,k} a_{i-1:j}^m$, $i=1, \dots, I$.
$\gamma_i(c)$	Activation function for layer i .
\mathbf{w}	Weight vector containing all weights $(w_{1:0,1}, w_{1:0,2}, \dots, w_{I:J_{I-1}, J_I})$

Architecture:

The general architecture for multilayer perceptron is:

Input layer: $J_0=P$ units, $a_{0:1}, \dots, a_{0:J_0}$; with $a_{0:j} = x_j$.

hidden layer: J_i units, $a_{i:1}, \dots, a_{i:J_i}$; with $a_{i:k} = \gamma_i(c_{i:k})$ and $c_{i:k} = \sum_{j=0}^{J_{i-1}} w_{i:j,k} a_{i-1:j}$ where $a_{i-1:0} = 1$.

Output layer: $J_I=R$ units, $a_{I:1}, \dots, a_{I:J_I}$; with $a_{I:k} = \gamma_I(c_{I:k})$ and $c_{I:k} = \sum_{j=0}^{J_{I-1}} w_{I:j,k} a_{i-1:j}$ where $a_{i-1:0} = 1$.

Note that the pattern index and the bias term of each layer are not counted in the total number of units for that layer.

Activation Functions

Hyperbolic Tangent

$$\gamma(c) = \tanh(c) = \frac{e^c - e^{-c}}{e^c + e^{-c}}$$

This function is used for hidden layers.

Identity

$$\gamma(c) = c$$

This function is used for the output layer when there are continuous targets.

Softmax

$$\gamma(c_k) = \frac{\exp(c_k)}{\sum_{j \in \Gamma_h} \exp(c_j)}$$

This function is used for the output layer when all targets are categorical.

Error Functions

Sum-of-Squares

$$E_T(w) = \sum_{m=1}^M E_m(w)$$

where

$$E_m(w) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{r=1}^R \left(y_r^{(m)} - a_{I:r}^m \right)^2$$

This function is used when there are continuous targets.

Cross-Entropy

$$E_T(w) = \sum_{m=1}^M E_m(w)$$

where

$$E_m(w) = - \sum_{r \in \Gamma^c} y_r^{(m)} \log \left(\frac{a_{I:r}^m}{y_r^{(m)}} \right)$$

This function is used when all targets are categorical.

Error Backpropagation

Error-backpropagation is used to compute the first partial derivatives of the error function respect to the weights.

$$\text{First note that } \gamma'(c) = \begin{cases} 1 - [\gamma(c)]^2 & \text{tanh} \\ 1 & \text{identity} \end{cases}$$

The backpropagation algorithm follows:

For each i, j, k , set $\frac{\partial E_T}{\partial w_{i:k,j}} = 0$.

For each m in group T ; For each $p=1, \dots, J_I$, let

$$\delta_{I:p}^m = \frac{\partial E_m}{\partial c_{I:p}^m} = \begin{cases} a_{I:p}^m - y_p^{(m)} & \text{if cross-entropy error is used} \\ \gamma'_I(c_{I:p}^m) (a_{I:p}^m - y_p^{(m)}) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

For each $i=I, \dots, 1$ (start from the output layer); For each $j=1, \dots, J_i$; For each $k=0, \dots, J_{i-1}$

$$\text{E Let } \frac{\partial E_m}{\partial w_{i:k,j}} = \delta_{i:j}^m a_{i-1:k}^m, \text{ where } \delta_{i:j}^m = \frac{\partial E_m}{\partial c_{i:j}^m}$$

$$\text{E Set } \frac{\partial E_T}{\partial w_{i:k,j}} = \frac{\partial E_T}{\partial w_{i:k,j}} + \frac{\partial E_m}{\partial w_{i:k,j}}$$

$$\text{E If } k > 0 \text{ and } i > 1, \text{ set } \delta_{i-1:k}^m = \gamma'_{i-1}(c_{i-1:k}^m) \sum_{j=1}^{J_i} \delta_{i:j}^m w_{i:k,j}$$

This gives us a vector of $\sum_{i=0}^{I-1} (J_i + 1) J_{i+1}$ elements that form the gradient of $E_T(w_k)$.

Gradient Descent

Given the learning rate parameter η_0 (set to 0.4) and momentum rate α (set to 0.9), the gradient descent method is as follows.

1. Let $k=0$. Initialize the weight vector to w_0 , learning rate to η_0 . Let $\Delta w_0 = 0$.

2. Read all data and find $E_T(w_k)$ and its gradient $g_k = \nabla E_T(w_k)$. If $|g_k| < 10^{-6}$, stop and report the current network.
3. If $\eta_k |g_k| \leq \alpha |\Delta w_k|$, $\alpha = 0.9 \eta_k \frac{|g_k|}{|\Delta w_k|}$. This step is to make sure that the steepest gradient descent direction dominates weight change in next step. Without this step, the weight change in next step could be along the opposite direction of the steepest descent and hence no matter how small η_k is, the error will not decrease.
4. Let $v = w_k - \eta_k g_k + \alpha \Delta w_k$
5. If $E_T(v) < E_T(w_k)$, then set $w_{k+1} = v$, $\Delta w_{k+1} = w_{k+1} - w_k$, and $\eta_{k+1} = \eta_k$, Else $\eta_k = .5\eta_k$ and return to step 3.
6. If a stopping rule is met, exit and report the network as stated in the stopping criteria. Else let $k=k+1$ and return to step 2.

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